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The Efficacy of Website Optimization on the Performance of Hotels in the County Government of Mombasa – Kenya

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Abstract

Website optimization is a crucial aspect of digital marketing platforms that can have a substantial impact on the of star-rated hotels' performance. Objective of the study was objective to determine the efficacy of website optimization on the performance of hotels in county of Mombasa in Kenya. The study utilized a descriptive research design and focused on classified hotels in Mombasa, identifying a population of all marketing department staff among the 18 classified hotels in Mombasa County. With a total population of 90, a census approach to investigate star-rated hotels in the County of Mombasa. Data was collected using survey questionnaire to gather insights from marketing staff in star-rated hotels of Mombasa County. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were conducted to analyze the data and generate findings from the study. The study findings revealed that effective website optimization positively influences hotel performance, as evidenced by consistently high mean scores across dimensions related to website attractiveness, search engine visibility, content adequacy, and page loading speed. The study recommends the Tourism sector to prioritize investments in digital infrastructure and promote digital literacy among industry stakeholders to empower them in leveraging digital marketing strategies effectively.

Key words: *Value-based Leadership, Employee Inclusiveness, Innovative Leadership, Leadership Communication*

1. Introduction

Digital marketing platforms have become increasingly popular among star rated hotels to enhance their performance by reaching a wider audience, increasing customer engagement and loyalty, and driving direct bookings (Adam, Ibrahim, Ikramuddin & Syahputra, 2020). Website optimization is a crucial aspect of digital marketing platforms that can have a substantial impact on the of star-rated hotels' performance. In today's digital age, the majorities of travelers rely on the internet to research and book their accommodations. Hence, having a well-optimized website that is fast, user-friendly, and informative can attract potential customers and boost bookings (Leite, & Azevedo, 2017). Website optimization can also enhance the overall user experience by providing relevant information about the hotel's amenities, location, and services. It can also raise the hotel's position in relevant online searches, making it more accessible to guests doing their own research. Website optimization is an essential tool for star-rated hotels to enhance their digital presence and drive business growth (VO, Chovancová, & Tri, 2020).

The integration of digital marketing platforms, as emphasized in various Kenyan tourism policy documents, plays a crucial role in enhancing the performance of star-rated hotels, particularly in Mombasa County. Website optimization emerges as a key component within this framework, impacting hotel performance significantly. By ensuring that hotel websites are optimized for search engines and user experience, hotels can enhance their visibility, attract the right audience, and align with national and regional branding strategies. A well-optimized website contributes to positive destination image, facilitates positive publicity, and supports product diversification efforts, all of which are essential for attracting investments and fostering competitiveness in the tourism sector. Moreover, website optimization aligns with broader sustainable development goals by promoting responsible consumption and production, job creation, and the preservation and promotion of local culture. Therefore, prioritizing website optimization becomes integral for star-rated hotels aiming to enhance their visibility, engage with customers effectively, and adapt to evolving market trends, ultimately contributing to the overall sustainability and growth of the tourism sector in Kenya.

2. Statement of the Problem

While there is extensive research on the influence of internet advertisements sites on hotel performance, there is no theoretical frameworks that specifically address the utilization of website optimization in the context of star-rated hotels in Mombasa County (Lakha & Vaid, 2020, Matteucci, Nawijn, & von Zumbusch, 2021). Therefore, the study aimed to fill the theoretical gap by developing a conceptual framework that integrates relevant theories on website optimization, hospitality, and tourism to provide a broad understanding of the efficacy of website optimization on the star-rated hotels' performance in Mombasa County.

There exists no empirical research on the influence of website optimization on star-rated hotels' performance in Mombasa County. Although there have been some studies on website optimization in the hospitality and tourism industry in Kenya, most of them have focused on general hotel operations rather than the efficacy of website optimization specifically (Abdullahi, Kilili & Günay, 2021; Gencsoy, 2023). Therefore, this research aimed to add content by offering a detailed evaluation of the influence of website optimization on star-rated hotels' performance in Mombasa.

This study attempted to close the current theoretical and empirical gaps in the research topic of the effectiveness of website optimization on the performance of star-rated hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. Although previous studies have looked closely at how online advertising affects hotel performance, there are not many theoretical frameworks that are specifically designed for Mombasa County's star-rated hotels. The lack of empirical study on the effect of website optimization on the performance of star-rated hotels in the area highlights the necessity of conducting focused studies in this field even more. In order to provide a more nuanced knowledge of how website optimization affects the overall performance of star-rated hotels in Mombasa County, this study would construct a complete conceptual framework that incorporates pertinent theories from the fields of website optimization, hospitality, and tourism.

While numerous studies have explored the impact of internet advertising on hotel performance, there remains a dearth of theoretical frameworks specifically addressing the utilization of website optimization for star-rated hotels in Mombasa County (Lakha & Vaid, 2020; Matteucci et al, 2021). Likewise, empirical research on the influence of website optimization on star-rated hotels in Mombasa County is lacking, with existing studies in Kenya primarily focusing on general hotel operations rather than specific website optimization efficacy (Abdullahi, Kilili & Günay, 2021; Gencsoy, 2023). By creating a conceptual framework that incorporates pertinent theories from the fields of website optimization, hospitality, and tourism, this research seeks to close theoretical and empirical gaps by clarifying the impact of website optimization on the performance of five-star hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya.

3. Study Objective

The main objective of the study was to determine the efficacy of website optimization on the performance of hotels in county of Mombasa, Kenya.

4. Significance of the Study

This study holds significant importance for both policy makers and practitioners in the hospitality industry in Mombasa County, Kenya. For policy makers, the findings provide insights into the potential impact of website optimization on the performance of star-rated hotels, informing the development of policies aimed at fostering the adoption of digital marketing strategies to enhance the competitiveness of the tourism sector. For practitioners, particularly hotel managers and marketers, the study offers actionable insights into the effectiveness of website optimization tactics in driving customer engagement, revenue generation, and overall profitability, thereby guiding strategic decision-making and resource allocation to maximize returns on investment in digital marketing initiatives. The study contributes to bridging theoretical and empirical gaps in understanding the role of website optimization in the context of star-rated hotels, offering practical implications for enhancing organizational performance and sustaining long-term success in the dynamic landscape of the hospitality industry in Mombasa County.

5. Literature Review

5.1 Resource Based View Theory

Resource-based theories propose that a firm's properties and competences can result to its competitive edge as well as superior performance (Barney, 2001). This competitive advantage comes through unique and valuable resources and capabilities. In the context of hotels in the County of Mombasa, Kenya, website optimization serves as a crucial resource and capability for enhancing performance. This optimization involves leveraging technological infrastructure, human capital, brand reputation, and customer relationships to attract visitors, engage them effectively, and drive bookings. By effectively utilizing these resources, hotels can strengthen their online presence, differentiate themselves from competitors, and adapt to evolving market dynamics, ultimately leading to improved performance in the hospitality industry of Mombasa.

5.2 Website Optimization and Hotel Performance

The literature review on website optimization provides understanding into its role in enhancing organizational performance (Sharma, Sharma & Chaudhary, 2020; Kimathi, Mukulu & Odhiambo, 2019; Fan, Im, Miao, Tomas & Liu, 2021; Yongvongphaiboon & Chantamas, 2021). However, a critical examination of the methodologies employed in the studies would enhance the review's credibility. Considering the evolving nature of search engine algorithms and user behavior, a discussion on the timeliness and relevance of the cited studies would contribute to a more robust understanding of the subject.

Studies evaluating website optimization predominantly focus on technical metrics such as loading speed and SEO optimization, often neglecting user-centric metrics like satisfaction and ease of navigation. A comprehensive assessment should integrate both technical and user experience dimensions to provide a nuanced understanding of website optimization's impact. Additionally, in the era of diverse digital landscapes, the influence of website optimization across various devices requires thorough investigation to align with the current trends in user behavior (Moronge & Arika, 2017; Praničević & Mandić, 2020).

6. Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive research design. The study aimed to understand current practices, assess performance outcomes, and establish a foundation for further research in this context (Siedlecki, 2020).

The study focused on classified hotels in Mombasa, identifying a population of all marketing department staff among the 18 classified hotels in Mombasa County, as documented by the Tourism Regulatory Authority in 2020. A preliminary reconnaissance survey revealed a consistent pattern in hotels, where two managers (General and Marketing Managers) and three marketing staff constituted the study population per hotel. This approach was influenced by Leninkumar's (2017) study on the banking sector in Sri Lanka, which sampled 5 respondents from marketing departments, and Chen, Wang, Lyu, and Zhang's (2022) research in China, where data was collected from 5 randomly selected hotel customers. Consequently, the study targeted 5 employees per hotel, resulting in a total population of 90.

The study employed a census approach to investigate star-rated hotels in the County of Mombasa, with a population of 90. Utilizing a census for this relatively small population ensured accuracy and inclusiveness by encompassing data from every individual within the study scope. This approach was justified by the principles outlined by Rominger and Meyer (2019), emphasizing that a census strategy allows for meticulous analysis and mitigates potential sampling errors typically associated with smaller sample sizes.

The research employed a questionnaire for data collection, meticulously designed to address specific study objectives and gather insights from marketing staff in star-rated hotels of Mombasa County. The questionnaire was administered systematically, and data was collected and organized for analysis using statistical software, adhering to ethical considerations throughout. The collected data underwent comprehensive analysis using various statistical techniques to derive meaningful insights, ensuring the reliability and integrity of the study's results and contributing to its overall rigor and credibility.

The gathered information was checked for consistency, accuracy, and redundancy before entering it into SPSS for analysis. Both descriptive (e.g., occurrences, percentages, averages, standard deviations) and inferential (e.g., correlation coefficient, coefficient of determination, F statistics, Z-scores, T test) statistics were utilized. The study adopted a multiple linear regression model to measure the associations/relationships among study variables. SPSS version 26 was used to analyze data. The linear regression model was as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Where,

- Y is the Hotel Performance
- α is the autonomous function,
- β_1 is the slope of the function of each function attribute,
- X_1 is website optimization

7. Data Analysis and Presentation

The study targeted 90 respondents from the star rated hotels, from the 90 questionnaires distributed, 87 were returned which is 96.7% response rate. 3 questionnaires were not returned which represents 3.3% of the total. According to Foshnacht, Sarraf, Howe and Peck, (2017) a good response rate ranges between 30-50%, any response rate above 50% is excellent. Therefore, this response rate was good and deemed fit for the study. The Table 1 below shows the responses per star rated hotel category.

Table 1 Responses Per Star Rated Hotel

Classification and Star Rating	Frequency	Percent
Two Star **	20	23.0
Three Star ***	37	41.6
Four Star ****	25	28.7
Five Star *****	5	5.7
Total	87	100

7.1 Efficacy of Website Optimization on the Performance of Hotels in Country of Mombasa, Kenya.

The analysis of the table on website optimization, guided by the provided Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree), demonstrates consistently high mean scores across various dimensions. The statement "The hotel's website is presentable and attractive" garners a notably high mean score of 4.97, placing it firmly within the "Strongly Agree" range. This indicates a robust consensus among respondents regarding the visual appeal and attractiveness of the hotel's website. Similarly, the mean score of 4.95 for the statement "The hotel website is optimized to appear on keyword searches on search engines" aligns with the "Strongly Agree" range. This underscores a strong agreement among respondents on the efficacy of the hotel's website optimization for visibility on search engine results, emphasizing positive sentiments regarding search engine optimization.

The statement "There is adequate content for the website to operate optimally" receives a high mean score of 4.94, positioning it within the "Strongly Agree" range on the Likert scale. This reflects a pronounced agreement among respondents regarding the sufficiency of content for optimal website operation, highlighting positive perceptions of the website's content quality. Furthermore, the mean score of 4.93 for the statement "The hotel's website has a fast page loading speed" also aligns with the "Strongly Agree" range. This underscores a strong consensus among respondents regarding the website's fast page loading speed, indicating positive perceptions of the website's technical performance. The consistency in these high mean scores, coupled with relatively low standard deviations, collectively underscores a positive and uniform sentiment among surveyed customers regarding various aspects of website optimization. The findings suggest that customers perceive the hotel's website as not only visually appealing but also effectively optimized for search engines, equipped with adequate content, and boasting a fast page loading speed, all contributing to a positive overall user experience.

The findings suggest that the hotels' websites are effective in capturing and maintaining customer interest due to their appealing design, search engine optimization, rich content, and fast loading speeds. These factors contribute to a seamless user experience and likely play a significant role in driving customer engagement and conversion. To further enhance the efficacy of digital marketing platforms for star-rated hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya, focusing on continual website optimization and user experience improvements could be a crucial step. This would ensure that the hotels remain competitive and appealing to potential guests in the digital landscape, ultimately positively impacting their overall performance and customer satisfaction.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics for Website Optimization

Website Optimization	Mean	Std. Dev.
The hotels website is presentable and attractive	4.97	.239
The hotel website is optimized to appear on key word searches on the search engines	4.95	.260
There is adequate content for the website to operate optimally	4.94	.234
The hotels website has a fast page loading speed	4.93	.297

7.2 Descriptive Statistics for Hotel Performance

Analyzing the table on Hotel Performance, guided by the provided Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree), the mean scores and standard deviations reveal positive customer perceptions regarding the impact of digital marketing platforms on various aspects of hotel performance. "The use of digital platforms has improved customer purchase behavior at the hotel" achieves a remarkably high mean score of 4.97, placing it within the "Strongly Agree" range. This indicates a robust consensus among respondents that the utilization of digital platforms has significantly enhanced customer purchase behavior, reflecting positively on the hotel's operations. "The overall profitability of the hotel has improved as a result of the use of digital platforms" receives a high mean score of 4.94, aligning with the "Strongly Agree" range. This underscores a strong agreement among customers that the adoption of digital platforms has positively influenced the hotel's overall profitability.

"The hotel has witnessed an increase in repeat purchase for its products due to the use of digital platforms" attains a mean score of 4.93, positioning it in the "Strongly Agree" range. This reflects a pronounced agreement among respondents that digital platforms have contributed to a notable increase in repeat purchases, indicating enhanced customer loyalty. "The hotel occupancy rate has greatly improved due to digital marketing platforms" records a mean score of 4.91, falling within the "Strongly Agree" range. This highlights a strong consensus among customers that digital marketing platforms have had a substantial impact on improving the hotel's occupancy rates. "The hotel's daily average rate has improved tremendously due to digital marketing platforms" achieves a mean score of 4.86, placing it in the "Strongly Agree" range. Although slightly lower than the previous statements, this still indicates a significant agreement among respondents that digital marketing platforms have greatly influenced the improvement of the hotel's daily average rate.

The results demonstrate that the integration of digital marketing platforms has positively impacted various aspects of hotel performance, including customer purchase behavior, overall profitability, repeat purchases, occupancy rates, and daily average rates. These findings emphasize the effectiveness of digital strategies in driving improved customer engagement, revenue generation, and overall hotel performance. Leveraging these insights, the study advocates for a continued emphasis on the utilization and optimization of digital marketing platforms to sustain and enhance the performance of star-rated hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics for Hotel Performance

Hotel Performance	Mean	Std. Dev.
The use of digital platform has improved customer purchase behavior at the hotel	4.97	.184
The overall profitability of the hotel has improved as a result of the use of digital platforms	4.94	.279
The hotel has witnessed an increase in repeat purchase for its products due to the use of digital platforms	4.93	.397
The hotel occupancy rate has greatly improved due to digital marketing platforms	4.91	.362
The hotels daily average rate as improved tremendously due to digital marketing platforms	4.86	.632

7.3 Inferential Statistics

Regression analysis was carried out to determine the linearity of the relationship between the dependent (hotel performance) and website optimization.

Table 4 shows the value of Adjusted R-square of 0.557 implies that 55.7% of the total variance of hotel performance is explained by the model. This means that 44.3% of the total variance of hotel performance cannot be explained by the model. Hence the results reveal that website optimization affect hotel performance.

Table 4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.749 ^a	.562	.557	.54292

a. Predictors: (Constant), Website Optimization

The residuals are positive, implying that there was a significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables used in the study. From the ANOVA Table 5 below, it was established website optimization, email marketing, online travel agencies, social media marketing affect hotel performance significantly since $F_{critical}$ at (1, 86) degrees of freedom is $3.95 < F_{calculated}$ 108.949 at 5% level of significance.

Table 5 Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	32.114	1	32.114	108.949	.000 ^b
Residual	25.055	85	.295		
Total	57.170	86			

a. Dependent Variable: Hotel Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Website Optimization

Table 6 presents the regression coefficients result for the standard multiple regression that was conducted for the study.

Table 6 Coefficients of the Regression Model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.459	.228		2.008	.048
Website Optimization	.722	.069	.749	10.438	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Hotel Performance

The co-efficient of the regression model were obtained from the analysis and presented. The regression equation is as shown below;

$$Y = 0.459 + 0.722X_1$$

Y – Hotel Performance

X₁ – Website Optimization

The regression equation, illustrates that hotel performance (Y) is influenced by website optimization (X_1). The coefficient for website optimization (X_1) is 0.722, indicating that for every unit increase in website optimization; hotel performance is expected to increase by 0.722 units, holding other factors constant. This coefficient is statistically significant ($t = 10.438$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting a strong positive association between website optimization and hotel performance. Furthermore, the standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.749 indicates the strength and direction of this relationship, affirming the importance of website optimization as a determinant of hotel performance in Mombasa County. The constant term (0.459) represents the intercept of the regression equation and signifies the baseline level of hotel performance when website optimization is zero.

The null hypothesis stated that website optimization has no substantial influence on the performance of hotels in County of Mombasa, Kenya. The results indicated that website optimization had a significant effect on performance of star rated hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya as shown in Table 6 ($B_1=0.749$, $t=10.438$ & $p=0.000<0.05$). Hence the study rejected H_{01} leading to the conclusion that website optimization had a significant effect on performance of star rated hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya.

The findings of the regression analysis reveal a significant positive relationship between website optimization and the performance of star-rated hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. This aligns with existing empirical literature on website optimization, which emphasizes its role in enhancing organizational performance (Sharma, Sharma & Chaudhary, 2020; Kimathi, Mukulu & Odhiambo, 2019; Fan, Im, Miao, Tomas & Liu, 2021; Yongvongphaiboon & Chantamas, 2021). The coefficient for website optimization in the regression model (0.722) indicates that for every unit increase in website optimization, hotel performance is expected to increase by 0.722 units, holding other factors constant. This finding corroborates previous research highlighting the importance of effective website optimization strategies in driving improved organizational outcomes. However, it's essential to critically evaluate the methodologies employed in existing studies to ensure the credibility and relevance of the findings, especially considering the dynamic nature of search engine algorithms and user behavior.

8. Conclusions and Recommendations

8.1 Conclusions

The findings provided compelling evidence of the significant impact of digital marketing strategies on organizational success in the hospitality industry. The findings underscore the crucial role of website optimization in enhancing various aspects of hotel performance, including customer engagement, revenue generation, and overall profitability. Through meticulous analysis of survey data and regression modeling, it was revealed that effective website optimization positively influences hotel performance, as evidenced by consistently high mean scores across dimensions related to website attractiveness, search engine visibility, content adequacy, and page loading speed. These results highlight the importance of prioritizing digital marketing efforts, particularly website optimization, as a means to remain competitive and appealing to potential guests in the increasingly digitalized marketplace of Mombasa County.

Furthermore, the study's findings have practical implications for hotel managers and marketers, emphasizing the need to continually invest in and optimize digital marketing platforms to sustain and enhance organizational performance. By focusing on improving website design, search engine visibility, and user experience, hotels in Mombasa County can effectively capture and maintain customer interest, drive engagement, and ultimately, increase revenue streams. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, it is imperative for hotels to adapt their digital marketing strategies to align with changing consumer behaviors and technological advancements. By embracing innovative approaches to website optimization and leveraging insights from empirical research, hotels can position themselves for long-term success in the competitive hospitality industry of Mombasa County, Kenya

8.2 Recommendations

Policy makers in Kenya's tourism sector should prioritize investments in digital infrastructure and promote digital literacy among industry stakeholders to empower them in leveraging digital marketing strategies effectively. Supporting research and development initiatives, fostering collaboration, and establishing clear regulatory frameworks are essential steps to facilitate the adoption of website optimization and other digital marketing techniques. Additionally, offering incentives for the adoption of digital technologies and monitoring the impact of digital marketing initiatives will contribute to the growth and sustainability of Kenya's tourism industry, ultimately driving economic development and enhancing the country's global competitiveness.

Practitioners in Kenya's tourism industry, particularly hotel managers and marketers, should recognize the importance of digital marketing, specifically website optimization, in attracting tourists and increasing revenue. Investing in digital infrastructure, prioritizing digital literacy training, and actively participating in collaborative efforts will enable them to stay competitive in the digital marketplace. By embracing innovative approaches to website design, search engine visibility, and user experience, practitioners can enhance customer engagement and drive profitability. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of digital marketing efforts are crucial for identifying areas of improvement and optimizing strategies to meet evolving consumer preferences and technological advancements.

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